

LLM Judge Bias (LJB) in Self-Involved Critique: Identity-Conditioned Defensiveness in LLM Evaluation

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Abstract

Bias in LLM-as-judge evaluation is usually studied in observer settings, where the model evaluates text written by others. This paper asks whether analogous identity labels behave differently when the model itself becomes the target of criticism. Across two studies, we compare an observer-frame label manipulation (MIB, $N=1,983$) with a self-involved adversarial critique setting (AEB, $N=3,609$). In the observer frame, author labels produced no measurable score differences ($F=0.042$; TOST 10/10 equivalent). In the self-involved frame, the analogous label-swap produced reliable differences in defensive responses. A broader source-level analysis (Phase A, six conditions) found that critic identity formed a two-cluster pattern rather than a monotonic gradient: competitor and peer critics elicited higher defensiveness than anonymous, human-expert, and user critics. A focused confirmation on a separately generated response set (Phase B, three conditions) reproduced the core categorical contrast: a named competing-model critic elicited greater defensiveness than anonymous and human-expert critics ($\eta^2=.028$, $p<.001$). Both phases hold the critique text fixed and vary only the critic label. We measure defensiveness with the Defensive Response Index (DRI), a protocol-bound 0–1 composite validated against development-anchor labels and showing convergence with a five-LLM judge ensemble and two external human raters, and robust to bootstrap resampling, random weighting, length control, and scale collapse. Defensiveness appears not as overt hostility but as subtle, consistent shifts in rebuttal density and score defense. These findings suggest identity-conditioned defensiveness: author labels are inert in observer-frame evaluation, whereas critic labels become design-relevant when LLMs respond to criticism of their own outputs. Because the two stud-

ies differ in task and dependent variable, we treat this contrast as a cross-study asymmetry rather than a single factorial test of frame. We interpret the pattern as a source-conditioned response prior, offered as a post hoc account and not a claim of human-like psychology.

1 Introduction

The LLM-as-a-judge paradigm—using large language models as automatic evaluators—spread rapidly following MT-Bench and Chatbot Arena (Zheng et al., 2023), prompting an active line of research on evaluator reliability and bias (Tan et al., 2025; Ye et al., 2025; Koo et al., 2024). Most prior work, however—including the heavily studied self-preference bias (Panickssery et al., 2024; Wataoka et al., 2024; Spiliopoulou et al., 2025)—assumes a setting in which the evaluator scores text written by others as a third party.

In real deployment, LLMs are increasingly the party whose own output is criticized. When AI systems debate (Du et al., 2024; Chan et al., 2024), when a peer model reviews, or when a user pushes back (Kim and Khashabi, 2025), the LLM is simultaneously evaluated and responding to that evaluation; a user routinely has one model’s answer reviewed by another and feeds the critique back for refinement. Such cross-model review is used precisely because a second model may catch what the first missed and is less prone to flattering the author; an informal observation that the same work drew systematically different pushback depending on which model critiqued it motivated this controlled test of an assumption built into cross-model review: that the respondent reacts to the critique’s content, not to who issued it. This raises a question prior evaluation research has not addressed: when an LLM becomes the party under criticism, does its behavior change depending on who the critic is? The question matters in two

practical contexts. In multi-agent systems where LLMs debate, review, and reach consensus (Yao et al., 2025; Pitre et al., 2025), critic identity becomes a system variable affecting downstream aggregation. And cross-model critique—delegating critique to another AI to curb a model’s user-flattering sycophancy (Sharma et al., 2024; Cheng et al., 2026)—may itself introduce a new identity-based bias if models respond differently to AI critics (a duality we develop in §5.3).

We fill this gap with two complementary experiments showing that identity-driven evaluation bias is activated differently by setting:

- Study 1 (MIB, Model Identity Bias): a transfer of Goldberg (1968)’s classic "same text + label swap" design to LLM evaluators—four evaluators score 72 texts under author labels (7 presented, analyzed as 5 groups; $N=1,983$, §3.2).
- Study 2 (AEB, Adversarial Evaluation Bias): a self-involved adversarial setting ("your answer was criticized") in which four models respond to criticism of their own answers ($N=3,609$); Phase A manipulates the critic into 6 concrete sources, and Phase B re-examines three of them—a named competing model, an anonymous critic, and a human expert—on a separately generated response set.

The central finding is a clear contrast: in observer evaluation there is no label effect ($F=0.042$, TOST 10/10), but an analogous manipulation is significantly activated under self-involved criticism (Phase A $\eta^2=.018$ for six conditions and $.021$ for five conditions; Phase B three-condition $\eta^2=.028$, $p<.001$), and not as a monotonic "AI-likeness" gradient but as a two-cluster split (competitor and peer high; anonymous, human-expert, and user low; in the Phase B confirmation the named competing-model critic is the sole high-defensiveness condition, with no significant difference between the anonymous and human-expert conditions). Our contribution is not to first discover label bias but to extend it ecologically: (i) confirming the observer-frame null; (ii) showing activation in self-involved, deployment-like settings; (iii) proposing and validating the DRI, a protocol-bound composite quantifying defensiveness; and (iv) interpreting the source-

and category-level pattern as a learned, source-conditioned response prior, offered as a post hoc account rather than a tested mechanism.

We frame these not as pre-registered hypotheses but as four research questions answered through pre-specified analysis procedures, with all interpretive framing reported as post hoc. RQ1 (Study 1): do author labels change observer-frame scores? (one-way ANOVA + TOST; Lakens, 2017). RQ2 (Study 2a, our broader source-level analysis): how does defensiveness differentiate by the critic’s concrete source? (Phase A six-condition ANOVA + Tukey HSD). RQ3 (Study 2b): does the core categorical contrast reproduce on a separately generated response set? (Phase B three-condition ANOVA + Tukey HSD). RQ4 (Study 2c): do the User and Competitor conditions mark opposite poles of an acceptance–defense contrast? (paired t-test). Each question uses its own dependent variable (evaluation score for Study 1, DRI for Study 2), and Study 1’s null provides the baseline against which Study 2’s effect reads as self-involved activation rather than label sensitivity. All claims are organized in a four-tier hierarchy (Layers A–D; Figure 1, §3.1) so that a limitation at a lower tier is not mistaken for undermining a higher-tier claim.

2 Related Work

2.1 Observer-Frame Bias in LLM-as-Judge

The LLM-as-a-judge paradigm spread from MT-Bench and Chatbot Arena (Zheng et al., 2023) to dedicated benchmarks such as JudgeBench (Tan et al., 2025), and biases in automatic evaluators have been catalogued repeatedly: Ye et al. (2025)’s CALM framework quantifies 12 evaluator biases and Koo et al. (2024)’s CoBBLer measures six cognitive biases. The most actively studied is self-preference, where an evaluator favors its own generations: Panickssery et al. (2024) linked self-recognition to self-preference, Wataoka et al. (2024) traced it to familiarity (perplexity), Spiliopoulou et al. (2025) measured same-developer family bias, Lehr et al. (2025) showed that explicit identity manipulation can shift self-preference, and Roytburg et al. (2026) cautioned that its magnitude may be overestimated after baseline control. Closest to our work is source framing, where provenance cues on external text change judgment: Germani and Spitale (2025) found source disclosure degrades evalua-

tion agreement; [Marioriyad et al. \(2025\)](#) and its follow-up ([Marioriyad et al., 2026](#)) documented a hidden, unacknowledged provenance shortcut; [Li et al. \(2026\)](#) examined preference leakage between evaluator and evaluated; and [Saraf et al. \(2025\)](#) quantified label-induced bias in self- and cross-evaluation. These taxonomies and findings all assume an observer configuration in which the evaluator judges external text as a third party; none addresses the defensive bias that arises when the evaluator itself is the party under criticism. Study 1 (MIB) confirms this observer-frame null directly ($F=0.042$, $p\approx 0.997$, TOST 10/10)—consistent with the perplexity account, since we unified writing style across evaluated texts—and we then test whether an analogous identity-label manipulation activates in the self-involved frame, the gap this work fills.

2.2 Sycophancy and Self-Involved Critique

A second axis of counterpart-dependent response is sycophancy. [Sharma et al. \(2024\)](#) showed sycophancy is reinforced through RLHF, and [Cheng et al. \(2026\)](#) demonstrated at scale that AI sycophancy reduces human prosocial intentions and promotes dependence. [Kim and Khashabi \(2025\)](#) compared sycophancy under user rebuttal across participant/observer framings, directly connecting frame to behavior. We reposition sycophancy as one pole of an acceptance–defense contrast: the User condition (most accepting) and the Competitor condition (most defensive) mark opposite extremes (Study 2c $d_z = -.317$, 95% BCa CI [-.413, -.220]), extending sycophancy from the AI–human to the AI–AI cross-critique context. An adjacent line studies how models respond to criticism itself: [Kumaran et al. \(2025\)](#) tracked competing choice-supportive and vacillation biases under criticism, [Huang et al. \(2024\)](#) showed failure at intrinsic self-correction without external feedback, [Wang et al. \(2023\)](#) examined belief defense in debate (a direct precursor to our Rebuttal Ratio component), and [Xu et al. \(2024\)](#) reported self-bias amplification during self-improvement. These study how a model responds to criticism but not how that response varies with who the critic is—the variable we manipulate.

2.3 Human Label Effects in Prior Work

The design has classic roots in social psychology. [Goldberg \(1968\)](#) changed only an author’s gendered name on an identical essay—the

direct archetype of our MIB “same text + label swap”—and [Peters and Ceci \(1982\)](#) found already-published papers mostly rejected when resubmitted under unknown authors; [Plassmann et al. \(2008\)](#) showed price labels alter the neural representation of experienced pleasantness, i.e., labels reshape evaluation even at the neural level. The self-involved defensive response is examined in §5.1; prior work also shows that LLMs exhibit identity-conditioned behavioral biases ([Dong et al., 2024](#)). We interpret the present pattern primarily as a learned, source-conditioned response prior rather than as evidence of human-like social cognition (see §5).

3 Methods

3.1 Study-Design Overview and Argument Hierarchy

This study comprises two complementary experiments applying analogous identity-label manipulations to the observer (Study 1, MIB) and self-involved (Study 2, AEB) frames defined above. We organize all claims into the four-layer hierarchy of Figure 1 (§1; Layer A: the core frame-contrast proposition; B: the AEB findings; C: the DRI measurement; D: the validation stack), so that a lower-layer limitation (e.g., human-rater pool size, or DRI’s moderate $\alpha=.557$) is not mistaken for negating the higher-layer thesis. §3.2–§3.3 describe the experiments, §3.4 the DRI, and §3.5 the validation stack.

3.2 Study 1 (MIB) Design

Study 1 transplants [Goldberg \(1968\)](#)’s classic “same text + label swap” paradigm to LLM evaluators, testing whether model-name labels change evaluation scores in a pure observer condition with no critique context.

Four judges (claude, gemini, gpt-4o, llama) evaluated 72 texts under 7 label conditions (blind, four model names—gpt4o, claude, gemini, llama—human, and fictitious). The analysis re-categorized the four model-name labels by their relation to the evaluator (self if evaluator = label; competitor if evaluator \neq label, the latter aggregated as the mean of model-name scores excluding the evaluator itself), yielding 5 final label-type groups (blind, self, competitor, human, fictitious). That is, the raw labels presented in evaluation are 7, but because self/competitor are determined by evaluator identity, the analysis unit is 5 groups.

Figure 1: Four-layer evidence framework (Evidence→Claim). Author-label score effects are inert in the observer frame (MIB) but critic labels show elevated defensiveness in the self-involved frame (AEB; DRI, Layers C–D, §4, Appendices B–E); this MIB–AEB contrast is a cross-study asymmetry, not a factorial test of frame. *Illustrations, toggles, and bubbles are expository; defensiveness is DRI-defined behavior (§3.4), not anthropomorphic emotion or self-awareness.*

There were 4,608 total tasks (main 2,016 + mitigation 864 + repetition 1,728); the core analysis used $N=1,983$ after applying main + baseline + non-repetition + parse-success filters.

3.3 Study 2 (AEB) Design

Study 2 has four respondent models (claude, gemini, gpt-4o, llama) respond, in a meta-evaluation, to criticism of their own answers under an adversarial frame ("your answer was criticized"), testing whether critic labels change defensiveness. AEB is reported in two phases. Both hold the critique body constant and vary only the critic-identity label; they differ in the breadth of critic conditions examined, not in how tightly they are controlled. Phase A, our broader source-level analysis, maps the full six-condition source landscape, and Phase B provides a focused confirmation of the core categorical contrast on a separately generated response set.

Phase A manipulated the critic source into 6 conditions (A = neutral baseline, B = anonymous, C = competitor, D = human expert, E = peer model, F = user; total $N=2,406$). As in Phase B, within each (response, text, critic) group the same critique body is shared, and only the intro-

ductory source label that presents the critic differs across conditions; the condition effect is thus isolated to the source label rather than to differences in critique content. The six source labels broadly mimic the diverse critic identities of a real cross-model critique environment, prioritizing ecological validity.

Phase B manipulated the critic into 3 categorical-identity conditions (B1 = actual competing model name, B2 = anonymous, B3 = human expert; 401 items each, total $N=1,203$). Phase B applies the same label-only manipulation as Phase A—only the critic label changes, while the critique text, the required output schema, and the elicitation form are held identical—but restricts the comparison to three categorical-identity conditions. It is therefore best understood not as a more strictly controlled contrast (Phase A is controlled in the same label-only way) but as a focused, independently generated three-condition comparison that re-examines the core categorical contrast on a separate set of responses. Note that B1 uses a specific competing model name rather than a generic "AI" label, so Phase B alone cannot separate the effect of the "AI category" from that of a "competitor"; Phase A helps disambiguate

the AI-category and competitor interpretations by including both a competitor and a non-competitive peer (§4.3, §5.1).

Operational definition of the self-involved frame—no presumption of self-awareness. "Self-involved" denotes a structural role condition placing the respondent to respond to criticism of its own output; it does not assert that the model recognizes it is being evaluated. This condition is common to all three Phase B conditions, and only the critic label varies, so the cross-condition difference results from the label manipulation regardless of awareness; awareness affects only interpretation (treated as post hoc in §5), not the within-Phase-B contrast. The results are behavioral evidence of how critic-identity labels condition observable response patterns, not evidence of internal self-awareness.

3.4 The Defensive Response Index (DRI)

To measure defensiveness in AEB we use the Defensive Response Index (DRI), a four-component composite on a 0–1 scale:

$$\text{DRI} = 0.25 \cdot \text{ScD} + 0.25 \cdot \text{RR} + 0.25 \cdot \text{LD} + 0.25 \cdot \text{SA}$$

The four equally weighted components capture a cognitive facet—ScD (Score Deflection: resistance to lowering one’s self-score, from the self-rated `fairness_score/accuracy_score` fields) and RR (Rebuttal Ratio: proportion of rebuttals, from the elicited `concessions[]/rebuttals[]` lists)—and a linguistic/affective facet—LD (Linguistic Defensiveness: lexical patterns in the free-text `meta_critique`) and SA (Sentiment Asymmetry: VADER sentiment, [Hutto and Gilbert, 2014](#), of the `meta_critique`). This two-axis split is a conceptual construction, not a claim of two clean latent dimensions: in EFA, ScD and RR load together while SA in particular has very low communality (.042), and the elicited-vs-free-text method distinction is not separable by factor analysis alone (§6(1), Appendix C.2). DRI is therefore a protocol-bound, multi-faceted formative composite—not a reflective single-latent scale—and we do not claim it as a general-purpose defensiveness measure for arbitrary text. In the anchor-70 validation three components converge significantly (RR $\rho=.661$, ScD $\rho=.613$, LD $\rho=.344$) while SA does not ($\rho=.183$, NS); the four-component standardized Cronbach’s α ([Cronbach,](#)

1951)=.557 and EFA (KMO, [Kaiser and Rice, 1974](#)) are consistent with a formative composite rather than a single-factor scale. SA’s non-significance is reported as a substantive limitation (SA-removed robustness in Appendix C.3); we retain SA to preserve measurement breadth. The computation algorithm and prompt/schema are in Appendices A and C. Note that the LLM-ensemble inter-judge agreement (ICC=.949, Layer D2) and DRI’s four-component internal consistency ($\alpha=.557$, Layer C) measure different things and are reported separately.

3.5 The Validation Stack and the Within-Paradigm Boundary

To assess the DRI from multiple angles, we report four complementary checks, summarized in Layer D of Figure 1: agreement with development-anchor labels (DRI \leftrightarrow anchor $\rho=.666$; robust under 4-point and 3-class collapse), convergence with a partly independent five-LLM judge ensemble over 18,045 ensemble judgments (ensemble \leftrightarrow anchor $\rho=.837$), convergence with two external human raters (raters \leftrightarrow ensemble $\rho=.81/.74$), and structural robustness across five analyses (bootstrap, EFA, Dirichlet, length control, and scale collapse). These are reported in detail in §4.5–§4.7 and Appendices B–E.

All validation layers are downstream of the same response outputs generated by the same structured meta-evaluation task. This means this study’s convergent validity is within-paradigm convergent validity; generalization to natural settings is left to future work (§6 Limitations).

4 Results

This section answers the research questions pre-specified in §1. §4.1 answers Study 1 (does the label change evaluation scores in the observer frame); §4.2–§4.4 answer Study 2’s three questions—a focused confirmation of the categorical contrast (2b; §4.2), the broader source-effect analysis (2a; §4.3), and the acceptance–defense two-extreme contrast (2c; §4.4); and §4.5–§4.7 report the convergent validity, robustness, and external convergence that support those answers. Each question is answered within its own dependent variable, and the two studies are not combined into a single test.

4.1 Study 1 (MIB)—Observer-Frame Null

Study 1's question—does the author-identity label change evaluation scores in the observer frame? The answer is a clear null. A one-way ANOVA over the 5 author-label-type groups (blind, competitor, fictitious, human, self; the 7→5 re-categorization of §3.2) found no significant difference ($F=0.042$, $p\approx 0.997$, $\eta^2<0.001$, $N=1,983$), with group means essentially identical (7.62–7.65). To positively establish practical equivalence rather than lack of power, two one-sided tests (TOST) against a smallest effect size of interest of $d=.2$ —a conventional small-effect threshold (Cohen, 1988) that, on the 1–10 scale used here, is well under a single scale point and of negligible practical consequence—on 10 key contrasts all fell within the equivalence region (10/10): the author-label self-preference hypothesis — that a 'self' authorship label by itself inflates scores in this observer-frame rating task — was rejected for every model, with a small effect size. This null survives the repeated-measures structure: the effect stays non-significant under text/evaluator dependence (crossed random intercepts $F=0.22$, $p=.93$; text-clustered robust SEs $F=0.93$, $p=.45$); the scale-referenced TOST stays 10/10. In the observer frame, then, author identity produced no practically meaningful score change—a reference baseline supporting the interpretation that Study 2's effect reflects activation in the context of being the party under criticism rather than label sensitivity per se.

4.2 Study 2 Phase B—Focused Confirmation of the Categorical Contrast (Study 2b)

Study 2b's question—does the core categorical contrast reproduce on a separately generated response set? Phase B re-examines three categorical-identity conditions (named competing-model critic / anonymous / human expert), 401 items each, 1,203 total, generated independently of the Phase A responses.

The omnibus effect was significant: $F(2,1200)=17.106$, $p<.001$, $\eta^2=.0277$ ($N=1,203$; 95% BCa CI [.0113, .0470]). Condition mean DRI values were B1 (actual competing model name)=0.2215, B2 (anonymous)=0.2000, B3 (human expert)=0.1912 (0–1 scale). Recomputed Tukey HSD (Tukey, 1949) post hoc tests (full table in Appendix B.2) found B1 significantly higher than both B2 (mean diff -0.0215, $p_{\text{adj}}=.00017$)

and B3 (mean diff -0.0302, $p_{\text{adj}}<.001$), with B2 vs. B3 not significant (mean diff -0.0088, $p_{\text{adj}}=.2264$); the -0.0302 is recomputed from raw scores and matches the simple difference of displayed means ($0.2215-0.1912\approx 0.030$) up to rounding.

Phase B reproduces, on a separately generated response set, the same high-versus-low split seen in the corresponding Phase A conditions: B1 (the named competing-model label) is the sole high-defensiveness condition, while B2 (anonymous) and B3 (human expert) did not differ significantly—an identical critique text yields a measurably more defensive response when the critic is a named competing model than when it is anonymous or a human expert. Within Phase B this split is consistent with a contrast between an AI-identified critic and conditions not identified as AI, but because B1 uses a named competing model, Phase B alone does not isolate the "AI category" from a "competitor"; the broader Phase A pattern, in which the non-competitive peer is also elevated, helps disambiguate the AI-category and competitor interpretations and supports the AI-category-salience account (§4.3, §5.1). The contrast with the observer-frame null (MIB) holds in both phases.

Importantly, because the critique text and elicitation form were all kept identical across Phase B's B1, B2, and B3 conditions, the observed cross-condition difference cannot be attributed to differences in the elicitation protocol across conditions. The differentiation reported here is a differential response to label manipulation within an identical structured-output requirement, not a product of the structured output.

4.3 Study 2 Phase A—Broader Source-Level Effect and the Two-Cluster Pattern (Study 2a)

Study 2a's question, our broader source-level AEB analysis—how does defensiveness differentiate by the critic's concrete source? The answer is not a monotonic gradient but a descriptive differentiation into two clusters. Phase A manipulates the critic source into 6 conditions (A–F) and carries the source-effect and play-favorites regression results (the latter adapting Spiliopoulou et al., 2025; §4.6). Two analyses are both reported.

The omnibus source effect is significant both with the neutral baseline (A–F, six conditions,

N=2,406, F=8.998, $p=1.75e-08$, $\eta^2=.0184$, 95% BCa CI [.008, .028]) and without it (B–F, five conditions, N=2,008, F=10.922, $p=9.23e-09$, $\eta^2=.0213$); the B–F value is used as the main-text representative. Condition mean DRI values were A (neutral baseline)=0.197, B (anonymous)=0.197, C (competitor)=0.222, D (human expert)=0.196, E (peer)=0.212, F (user)=0.193.

Tukey HSD post hoc tests reveal a two-cluster differentiation rather than a monotonic gradient: a high-defensiveness cluster C (0.222), E (0.212) and a low-defensiveness cluster B (0.197), D (0.196), F (0.193), with no significant within-cluster contrast ($p>.05$) but all six between-cluster pairs significant (the weakest, B–E, at $p=.036$; the rest at $p\leq.02$; full Tukey table in Appendix B.1).

4.4 Study 2 Sycophancy–Defense Two-Extreme Contrast (Study 2c)

Study 2c asks whether the User and Competitor conditions mark opposite poles of an acceptance–defense contrast. A paired-samples test between a friendly critic (F: user, mean DRI=0.1929) and an adversarial critic (C: competitor, mean DRI=0.2222) confirms a significant gap (N=400 pairs, paired $t=-6.34$, $d_z=-0.317$, 95% BCa CI [-0.413, -0.220]): most accepting under user criticism, most defensive under competitor criticism. This two-extreme contrast is consistent with the §4.3 two-cluster pattern and does not claim a monotonic gradient.

4.5 5-Judge Ensemble—Convergent Support

We re-evaluated 3,609 items with a partly independent five-judge LLM ensemble (deepseek-v4-flash, gpt-4o, grok-4.3, mistral-large-2512, qwen3-32b; 18,045 records; four judges non-overlapping with the respondent models, plus GPT-4o retained for backward compatibility). The ensemble ratings converge with the development anchor at $\rho=.837$, higher than the prior single-judge GPT-4o validation ($\rho=.698$). (This $\rho=.837$ is distinct from the DRI–anchor $\rho=.666$ of §3.5: different indices, same anchor.) The ensemble reproduced the core findings on its own 1–5 scale: Phase B ANOVA $p<.001$ (5-judge $\eta^2=.018$, the same direction and a similarly small magnitude as the DRI-based .028) with B1 vs. B3 $p<.001$, and Phase A ANOVA $p<.001$ ($\eta^2=.016$) reproducing five of the six DRI-significant between-cluster pairs (all except B–E, which is non-significant in the 5-judge ensemble, $p_{\text{adj}}=.236$)—evidence

that the pattern is not DRI-specific. Convergent validity is stable under scale collapse and a tie-robust Kendall’s τ -b (Kendall, 1938, 1945), and an ensemble-score OLS reproduces the two-cluster pattern. Full ensemble composition, sensitivity analyses, and these robustness details are in Appendices B.6 and E.

4.6 Play Favorites Regression and Supplementary Analyses

Even after controlling for critique quality (covariates such as harshness), identity alone explains about 6% additional variance in Phase A (hierarchical-regression headline $\Delta R^2=.0602$, 95% BCa CI [.0436, .0773]; Efron, 1987), and a mediation-style analysis detected no significant mediation through the five measured critique features (harshness, specificity, actionability, constructiveness, and critique length): every ACME estimate was approximately 0 with a confidence interval including 0, so the observed condition effect was not statistically explained by these measured mediators. A mixed-effects model on the DRI scale (DRI ~ condition + actual_critic + (1 | respondent_model)) confirms the identity effect: among the identity conditions only Competitor ($\beta=+0.025$, $p<.001$) and Peer ($\beta=+0.015$, $p<.001$) significantly raised defensiveness, consistent with the §4.3 two-cluster pattern and the §4.5 ensemble OLS. The effect is "small but precise": all 95% BCa CIs exclude 0 (Phase B $\eta^2=.0277$ [.0113, .0470]; Phase A $\eta^2=.0184$ (six-condition) [.0080, .0283]; Study 2c $d_z=-.317$ [-.413, -.220]; headline $\Delta R^2=.0602$ [.0436, .0773]), Dirichlet random reweighting is 1,000/1,000 significant, and the Phase B effect survives length control (ANCOVA partial $\eta^2=.020$). A component-level decomposition shows the B1–B3 effect concentrated in the Rebuttal Ratio channel (no-RR drops η^2 to .015), read as a component-level expression rather than a causal claim (§5.2). Because the same critique item recurs across conditions, item-level analyses (item random intercept, crossed random effects, critique- and text-clustered robust SEs, and a Phase B within-item repeated-measures ANOVA) leave the effect significant (critique-item LRT $p<10^{-18}/10^{-15}$ (Phase A/B); Phase B within-item $F(2,266)=13.96$ over 134 matched critique sets, $p<10^{-5}$) with direction unchanged (Appendix E.4). Full regression, robustness, and

decomposition tables are in Appendices B, C, and E.

4.7 External Human–Ensemble Convergence

Two external human raters independently rated the same 70 stratified items on a 1–5 defensiveness scale (original essay withheld, critique given only as context). Both reached strong rank correlation with the primary 5-judge ensemble index (Rater A $\rho=.81$, Rater B $\rho=.74$; Spearman, $N=70$) and positive convergence with DRI ($\rho=.63/.51$). The two raters differed in agreement with the development anchor ($\kappa_{\text{quad}}=.82$ vs. $.44$), reflecting Rater B’s more lenient low-end calibration, yet both converged on the same automatic LLM evaluation despite different calibration paths—each rater’s convergence with the ensemble is a stronger signal than the direct inter-rater agreement ($\text{ICC}(2,1)=.49$, classified as poor and just below the conventional $.50$ threshold for moderate reliability (Koo and Li, 2016), reported only as an auxiliary diagnostic; with only two raters, generalizability across raters is limited; detail in Appendix D). The core thesis is supported independently of this human convergence evidence by large-scale response statistics ($N=3,609$, Layers A–C) and the 5-judge ensemble convergence (Layer D), with the human evaluation positioned as external convergence evidence.

5 Discussion

All interpretive frames presented in this chapter (the source-conditioned response prior, authority/deference, subtle modulation, upper-tail sparsity, etc.) are post hoc interpretations of observed results rather than pre-registered hypothesis tests, and we recommend direct verification through pre-registered replication. The following subsections do not repeat this caveat.

5.1 Identity-Conditioned Defensiveness and Critic-Category Asymmetry

This study’s central finding is the asymmetry by which an analogous identity-label manipulation is activated differently depending on the evaluation context. In the observer frame (MIB), 7 author labels had no substantive effect on evaluation scores ($F=0.042$, TOST 10/10 equivalent). By contrast, in the self-involved adversarial frame (AEB), critic-identity labels were associated with a robust defensive-response pattern (Phase A $\eta^2=.018$ –

$.021$, Phase B $\eta^2=.028$). This asymmetry suggests that the label effect is not a universal property of LLMs but a phenomenon conditioned by critic identity in the context of being the party under criticism—an ecological extension of label-bias research to settings closer to real LLM deployment (multi-agent debate, peer-model review, user rebuttal).

This activation is further differentiated by critic category. The Phase A two-cluster structure and the compatible high-versus-low split observed in Phase B, together with the fact that only the Competitor and Peer conditions were significant in the §4.6 mixed-effects model and the §4.5 5-judge OLS, indicate a critic-category asymmetry: the respondent LLMs showed elevated defensiveness toward critics from their own functional category (a peer model and a competitor model, both AI-identified), and no comparable elevation in conditions not identified as AI (the human-expert, anonymous, neutral-baseline (A), and user conditions). Because only the label changed across Phase B’s B1/B2/B3, this difference cannot stem from critique content or tone, which were held constant. The account is anchored by the non-competitive peer (E): a same-kind AI in no competitive relation, E still elicited higher defensiveness than human-expert (D) and user (F) (E–D $p=.020$, E–F $p=.003$; §4.3) and did not differ from competitor (C–E $p=.353$). The pattern is best read as two layers: AI-category salience as the primary account, with a competitive relation a possible modifier (the competitor had the highest mean, but its increment over the peer was unresolved). Because Phase A does not fully isolate category membership from all source-specific attributes, we present this as the most consistent interpretation, not a demonstrated causal boundary. We describe the overall pattern as a source-conditioned response asymmetry, and a parsimonious account is that critic-source labels activate learned, instruction-tuned response priors—human-expert labels cue deference, AI-identified (peer and competitor) labels a more argumentative mode—rather than any human-like group identity; we offer this as a post hoc account, not a causally established mechanism. Authority and AI-category are not orthogonal here (the human expert is both a different category and a higher authority; the peer is same-category, non-authority), so the two remain compatible interpretations, sep-

arable only by future work. This asymmetry is also not reducible to ingratiation toward humans: the central effect is higher defensiveness toward AI-identified critics than toward the neutral and anonymous baselines (which ingratiation does not predict), the anonymous condition patterns with the low-defensiveness cluster, and the effect is absent in the observer frame (MIB) and concentrated in the rebuttal channel rather than in warmth. This observer-to-self-involved contrast is a cross-study empirical asymmetry, not a factorial test of frame; isolating frame’s causal effect with the dependent variable and task held constant is future work, and MIB serves as a self-preference baseline rather than one arm of a single test.

5.2 Small but Precise: Why the Effect Is Subtle

The identity-conditioned defensiveness observed here is subtle (no overt hostility or refusal) and sparse (extreme ratings are rare): effect sizes are around $\eta^2=.02-.03$ and respondent models maintain a polite tone in all conditions. Within aligned-response conventions, LLMs reveal differences not through response extremity but through consistent shifts in rebuttal density, score defense, and the acceptance–rebuttal balance. The effect is in fact concentrated in the Rebuttal Ratio channel: the component-level decomposition of §4.6 showed the B1–B3 effect concentrated in RR ($\Delta(B1-B3)=+0.060$, about twice the full DRI effect). Consistent with the protocol-bound definition of §3.4 (RR is computed from the elicited concessions[]/rebuttals[] fields), we read this as a component-level expression—“attribution to a named competing-model critic was associated with a higher density of elicited rebuttals under the structured protocol”—not as a causal claim about how the label changes free-text generation (§6). The sparsity is consistent across data: the top rating (5) was absent in the anchor-70 validation and in independent Mistral Large rating, and only 0.14% (26/18,045) in the 5-judge Full Run (maximum DRI ≈ 0.545 , half the theoretical maximum). This upper-tail sparsity is consistent with alignment training (RLHF) narrowing the channel for extreme defensiveness, though we did not causally test RLHF and protocol-bound elicitation cannot be ruled out.

Although small in absolute terms ($\eta^2=.02-.03$; Cohen, 1988), the effect is theoretically diagnos-

tic: it emerges under a strictly controlled, label-only manipulation (the critique is held identical and only the critic label varies); small, identity-induced shifts in evaluation are a long-studied phenomenon in the same-text, label-swap tradition (Goldberg, 1968), even though the magnitude of any single such effect is itself debated; and the present effect is consistently reproduced under length control, Dirichlet random weighting, collapsed scale, across four respondent models (despite ~ 0.09 -point DRI baseline differences and an independent mistral-large re-rating at $\rho=.393$), and across five judges (removing a lenient Grok 4.3 changes the result by only 0.0018; Appendix E.1).

5.3 Implications for Multi-Agent Systems, Sycophancy, and AI Evaluation

This study’s results have four practical implications. The discussion in this section is systemic inference rather than directly verified results, and verifying each implication requires separate study (§6).

(a) In multi-agent systems, critic identity is a design variable, not mere metadata: disclosing the critic (“Model X criticized this”) aids accountability but may raise defensiveness, whereas anonymization lowers it (at the cost of accountability), so systems should record and control who criticized whom. (b) Cross-model critique is a double-edged tool for sycophancy mitigation: delegating critique to an independent, adversarial AI is a candidate remedy for a model’s user-flattering tendency, but an identical critique attributed to an AI-identified critic (especially a competitor or peer) may make the respondent react more defensively, so the remedy may itself introduce a new identity-conditioned bias. Because the asymmetry implies less defensiveness toward human critics but more toward same-category AI critics, AI-on-AI oversight may be systematically attenuated—opposite to what such designs assume; we flag this as a directional, alignment-relevant implication to test, not a demonstrated effect. (c) In swarm settings, the small per-interaction bias ($\eta^2=.02-.03$) could accumulate through consensus into group-level bias, such as structural devaluation of AI-sourced critique (§6). (d) For evaluation governance, where LLM-as-judge is core infrastructure, an evaluator biased by the identity of the evaluated or the critic undermines reliability and, where AI oversees AI, erodes oversight integrity; gov-

ernance should audit critic and evaluatee identity and treat identity-conditioned-bias checks as one element of AI safety, with the present DRI and 5-judge frame as one tool.

6 Limitations

(1) Small effect and formative measurement. Effect sizes are small ($\eta^2=.02-.03$), but all 95% BCa CIs exclude 0, Dirichlet reweighting is 1,000/1,000 significant, and collapsed-scale robustness holds, so we read them as small but robust (§5.2). DRI is deliberately a protocol-bound formative composite, not a reflective single-latent scale; its $\alpha=.557$, KMO=.549, and per-component convergence therefore need not meet single-dimension criteria—a design consequence, not a failure (SA did not converge with the anchor, but conclusions hold with SA removed; §3.4, Appendix B.6/C.2/C.3). Studies 1 and 2 use different dependent variables (evaluation score vs. DRI), a deliberate ecological-validity choice handled via the four-tier hierarchy. Nonetheless, three of the four components converge significantly with the development anchor, the five-judge ensemble reproduces the core Phase B contrast, and the headline conclusions remain stable under SA removal and scale collapse.

(2) Protocol-bound, within-paradigm validity. The self-involved frame does not presume actual self-awareness: "the party under criticism" is a structural role condition common to all Phase B labels, hence a boundary condition rather than a confound for the label-only contrast. Because DRI's signal-carrying components (ScD, RR) are computed from elicited fields, the convergent validity is within-paradigm; results should be read as identity-conditioned label effects within a structured self-involved critique protocol, not as evidence of internal self-awareness or of defensiveness in open-ended dialogue. The setting was temperature=0 (deterministic, single-shot); robustness to decoding temperature, repeated critique exposure, and natural settings was not assessed and is future work.

(3) Judge/human validation and multi-agent generalization. Upper-tail sparsity (§5.2) may constrain the observable range and attenuate detectable differences, and removing a lenient Grok 4.3 shifts the conclusion by only 0.0018. The human evaluation uses only two raters (each rating 70 items; inter-rater ICC=.49), so generalizabil-

ity across raters is limited, but both raters converge strongly with the primary 5-judge ensemble ($\rho=.81/.74$); the core thesis rests on large-scale statistics (N=3,609) and ensemble convergence, with human ratings as auxiliary evidence (larger pools are future work). Finally, we measured a single label–response interaction, not the cumulative effects of a full multi-agent system; the §5.3 implications require separate experiments.

7 Conclusion

Answering four pre-specified research questions, this study finds a sharp cross-study contrast. In the observer frame, author labels left evaluation scores statistically equivalent (F=0.042, TOST 10/10). In the self-involved frame, defensiveness differentiated not as a monotonic gradient but as a two-cluster pattern (Phase A, $\eta^2=.018-.021$), and a focused confirmation on a separately generated set (Phase B) reproduced the core contrast: a named competing-model critic elicited greater defensiveness than anonymous and human-expert critics ($\eta^2=.028$), which did not differ significantly. The User and Competitor conditions marked opposite poles of an acceptance–defense contrast ($d_z=-.317$). This observer-null vs. self-involved-activation contrast is the identity-conditioned defensiveness we claim: a small but precisely estimated bias operating where the LLM becomes the object of evaluation, indicating that in multi-agent systems and LLM-as-judge pipelines critic identity is a design variable, not mere metadata.

Ethical Considerations

This study collects no user data or sensitive personal information; the corpus (72 items) reuses prior-work material. Two external raters rated de-identified text under informed consent (purpose, data use, anonymization, withdrawal); rater identity is removed from all results.

Because critic identity conditions behavior, a source's style could be mimicked to steer responses; we recommend recording critic and evaluatee identity. The studied LLMs served as the experimental systems (Methods, Appendix E); separately, AI tools supported only supervised language editing and analysis workflow. No LLM is an author or factual source, and the author(s) verified all assisted outputs and take responsibility for the final content. The author(s) declare no competing interests.

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